

REFLECTIONS OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY IN THE SOCIAL GOSPEL ROLE OF THE ADVENTIST DEVELOPMENT AND RELIEF AGENCY IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Faith-based non-governmental organisations (NGOs) are institutions that are wholly owned by religious institutions or private individuals with core faith-oriented values. As not-for-profit organisations, they perform evangelistic functions using the mode of the social gospel in a manner akin to corporate social responsibility (CSR). To this end, they approach their roles from the compassionate eye of Jesus, by seeking to alleviate poverty and promote development that will engender just and positive changes. Nevertheless, for some reasons, these organisations have hardly achieved their goal to the fullest at any time. The Adventist Development and Relief Agency in Nigeria (ADRA-Nigeria) is one of such NGOs described in the foregoing comments. This paper explored the activities of ADRA-Nigeria to assess how effectively it has fulfilled its core mission as a faith-based NGO, focusing on its social gospel efforts as legitimate CSR initiatives benefiting the Nigerian populace. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design, which incorporated the use of in-depth, key informant interviews (KII) for data collection from the Director and five beneficiaries of ADRA services located in the Northeastern Nigerian states of Adamawa, Borno, and Yobe ravaged by Boko Haram terrorism. Qualitative analysis of the data revealed that ADRA-Nigeria has been rendering non-discriminate social services to vulnerable people in the study areas; its operations tally with the concept of CSR; and the institution has become socially relevant through its social gospel activities. Consequently, the paper concludes that ADRA-Nigeria has lived up to expectation through its social gospel cum CSR functions in Northeastern Nigeria.

Keywords: Adventist Development and Relief Agency, Corporate Social Responsibility, Faith-Based NGOs, Humanitarianism, Nigeria, Social Gospel.

INTRODUCTION

Adventist Development and Relief Agency (ADRA) an arm of the global body of the Seventh-day Adventist Church, was established in November 1966 as a faith-based non-governmental organisation. ADRA has its worldwide headquarters in Silver Spring, Maryland in the United States of America. It has branches in more than 120 countries of the world, including Nigeria, with the same purpose of providing humanitarian assistance to the most disadvantaged people through its social gospel activities across the various places of its existence around the globe (Hirata et al., 2021; PMNCH, 2022). Adventist Development and Relief Agency in Nigeria

(ADRA-Nigeria), which is the focus of this paper, was registered in 1990 with the Corporate Affairs Commission as a faith-based non-governmental organisation. Since then, it has functioned to reach Nigerian citizens with humanitarian aid, through its social gospel activities, that double as corporate social responsibility (CSR). The ultimate aim has been to achieve the practical aspect of the gospel, which has to do with contributing to the provision of the material needs of humanity alongside its spiritual needs for the ultimate and holistic preparation of God's children for His Kingdom.

The present security situation and the accompanying extreme hardship in Nigeria seem to be a large stumbling block to the achievement of the goals of ADRA-Nigeria. Moreover, it is one thing for an organisation to set goals, but a different thing entirely for them to be able to achieve it as expected, especially in the face of uncertainties. In fact, many Christian organisations have continued to emphasise the need for charity work in line with the scriptures. In doing this, they either embark on it directly as a Church activity or they use their parastatals to engage in charitable works to their host communities and the entire society at large depending on the capacity and felt need of the society. Sometimes, while rendering this otherwise free and voluntary service, the target recipients may misunderstand the good intentions of the giver. They may be apprehensive of the fact that it could be a bait to lure them into becoming members of the Church of the donor organisation. More often than not, such fears may also prove to be real. Therefore, it has become necessary to highlight the extent to which ADRA-Nigeria has been achieving its goal amidst the stated challenges and problems, especially in the terrorist battered Northeastern states of Nigeria. Thus, this paper evaluated the activities of ADRA-Nigeria in the context of the extent to which it has been able to fulfil its mission within the timeframe of this study. The questions designed to effectively execute this evaluation are as follows.

1. In what ways does ADRA-Nigeria present its social gospel in relation to the practice of corporate social responsibility?
2. How do the recipients perceive the corporate social responsibility efforts of ADRA-Nigeria in relation to their needs?
3. What challenges, if any, has affected the success of ADRA-Nigeria in presenting the social gospel through her corporate social responsibility efforts?
4. To what extent can ADRA-Nigeria be adjudged to have been successful in its social gospel efforts, especially in Nigeria's Northeastern states?

Conceptual Framework

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

As a management concept, corporate social responsibility advocates the need for an organisation to show a deep sense of concern and identification with its host community (Umar et al., 2022). It calls firms to be aware of their indebtedness to the society. It maintains that there should be a sense of commitment by business organisations to the needs and aspirations of the environment of their operation. Through such commitments, CSR becomes a form of

image building strategy and reputation enhancer for business organisations (Demeke & Ravi, 2024). With time, it becomes a means of making more money/profit. Companies that engage in CSR can attest to the fact that it aids longevity and helps promote their brand activities. CSR offers benefits to both the society and the organisations involved. When Churches and their affiliate bodies engage in CSR, they do so not out of the expectation of material benefit but because it is part of the doctrines of the Church – alms giving, helping one another in diverse ways.

Faith-based Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs)

Faith-based non-governmental organisations (NGOs) are not-for-profit institutions that have strong affiliations with religious organisations. They are either fully owned or managed as an arm of known religious organisations or as independent bodies owned by individuals or groups of people that subscribe to the values espoused by a known religious body (Chowdhury et al., 2019; Noor, & Nawi, 2023). When a faith-based NGO is fully owned by a religious body, it primarily derives its funding, regulation, and guidance from that religious body. But when owned by either an individual or group(s) who subscribe to the basic tenets of a certain religious organisation, the NGO will be funded by its owner(s), but be reasonably influenced by the policies of the affiliated religious organisation of its owner(s). Accordingly, Christian faith-based NGOs may subscribe to the values of a certain Christian denomination or may just derive their values from the general Christian principles. Whichever is the case, one thing that is common among Christian faith-based NGOs is that, in ideal cases, they are established to present Jesus Christ to the world through the rendering of social services to the individual and the society in which they operate. It is in this wise that they propagate the social gospel of “love your neighbour as yourself”. By so doing, they work freely and wholeheartedly help individuals and groups in such areas as peace building, humanitarian needs, and thereby contribute to national development.

Humanitarianism and Social Gospel

Humanitarianism is a concept that implies the perception that people are meant to help improve the lives of their fellow human beings in any way they can. According to Fraser and Murakami (2021), humanitarianism is the “belief that people have responsibilities towards their fellow human being and should come to the assistance of others in need” (p. 259). It is also the commitment of an individual or group to act in ways that are ultimately beneficial to other people and their communities at large. According to International Association of Professionals in Humanitarian Assistance and Protection (PHAP), humanitarianism is the belief in and practice of far-reaching commitment to the fundamental value of human life and the active support for it at all times. It is a systemic response to crisis, which involves the act of “addressing the needs of people affected by conflict, natural disaster, epidemic and famine” (PHAP, 2020, para. 1). Its phenomenal ethics of operation cuts across cultures. The concept evolved as a prominent social issue of concern across the globe over 150 years ago from the founding of the Red Cross and the First Geneva Convention in connection with western crisis (PHAP, 2020).

On the other hand, the concept of social gospel started with a Christian movement in the United States of America during the 19th Century (Steensen, & Villadsen, 2020). It is a humanitarian process which sought to use Biblical principles of justice to address social injustice and inequality. Walter Rauschenbusch who is acknowledged as one of its foremost proponents maintains that the application of the three main Christian virtues of love, service and equality are vital to redressing social injustice for the ultimate achievement of social action and change (William, 2019). Washington Gladden, another proponent of the social gospel emphasises how Christians should think, act and respond to social issues (William, 2019). Although these two leading advocates of the social gospel may have emphasised socio-political actions, later advocates, such as Dorothy Day, laid emphasis on social relationships. For her, leading a life of poverty and choosing to live and associate with the poor and deprived is a very eloquent testimony of the social gospel. This may have informed the charity work of the late Mother Theresa (1910-1997), who chose to live a life of service among the downtrodden of India and literally gave her life for this cause. Social gospel is one of the most impactful religious movements of the 20th century that still has great impact today. This is because of its aim of bringing about social transformation guided by Bible-based ethical values. This is with a view to transforming the society to one that prioritises and promotes the well-being of the individual in the society (Steensen, & Villadsen, 2020; Darmawan, 2023).

From the foregoing, it is obvious that humanitarianism and social gospel have the same meaning or implication, except for the fact that while humanitarianism may have a secular and political orientation, social gospel always has a religious foundation. This does not mean that social gospel may not be carried out for some political reasons when and where necessary. They both focus on improvement of people and their society as well as protection of lives and by implication, property (especially those that aid the protection of life and alleviation of human sufferings). Humanitarianism, when practiced by Christians in obedience to their faith, is social gospel. One of the tenets of Christianity is to follow in the footsteps of our Lord Jesus Christ, Who during His time on earth reached out to the needy by helping their physical needs, feeding multitudes, and granting healing to the sick. The Church, as a body of Christ, has taken up the responsibility of responding to the social needs of the people through fight against poverty, child labour, and gender discrimination (MacDonald, 2019). It has also assumed the responsibility of contributing to reduction of slums and unclean environments and provision of aid to displaced individuals. All these have been in a bid to manage societal challenges and to align its spiritual responsibility to that of the society (Ballor & Joustra, 2016). The social welfare programmes of the Church are ways by which the social gospel is applied today. It is based on the Christian virtue of love, peace and compassion.

The Nexus between Social Gospel and Corporate Social Responsibility

The social gospel efforts of Christian faith-based NGOs can be compared to corporate social responsibility (CSR) practices. Jintao et al. (2020) categorise CSR activities into four key areas: economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities. These areas define how organisations meet their obligations to society by balancing profitability with adherence to legal standards, ethical practices, and philanthropic contributions. Similarly, Al-Ma'ani et al.

(2019) highlight the focus of CSR on environmental, customer, and community dimensions, emphasising the role of organisations in addressing environmental concerns, meeting customer needs, and contributing to community development. In this context, Christian faith-based NGOs engage in social gospel work that parallels CSR by addressing community needs through ethical and philanthropic initiatives inspired by their religious values. For Christian faith-based NGOs, CSR is an obligation, and indeed, a divine injunction to translate the gospel to acts of charity and human kindness.

Drawing from the general concept of reaching and identifying with the host community, individual business organisations determine what motivates them to reach out in their CSR efforts. When business organisations show compassion to their host communities through CSR, they will in turn, reap the benefit of profitable financial market. This echoes the Biblical injunction of ‘cast your bread upon the waters, for you will find it after many days’ (Ecclesiastes 11:1 KJV). Whereas secular organisations engage in CSR for material benefit of enhancement of corporate image and reputation (Tian et al., 2020), faith-based NGOs are rather motivated to engage in CSR as a response to Jesus’ sermon on the mount when He enjoined thus, ‘Let your light so shine before men, that they may see your good works and glorify your Father in heaven’ (Matthew 5:16, NKJV).

CSR contributes to the brand and goodwill of an organisation or institution (Pallathadka & Pallathadka, 2022). Even when the institution is a non-profit one like faith-based NGOs, the brand image and goodwill of the parent body of the faith-based NGO becomes continuously enhanced through every effort they make in reaching the society by meeting their needs. This is the reason many organisations are actively participating in the practice. Embedding CSR in faith-based organisations has the potential of taking the gospel far beyond where the most eloquent and charismatic preacher could reach. Corporate social responsibility stands on the ethical and theological foundations of the laws of God (Raimi et al., 2014). Secular organisations and corporations often engage in corporate social responsibility (CSR) due to legal requirements or pressure from host communities. In contrast, faith-based NGOs voluntarily participate in CSR as a means of expressing and sharing the love of God, without any legal obligation. This perspective aligns with the findings of Setiawan et al. (2021) and Sessa et al. (2020), who argue that Churches engage in CSR primarily to enhance their ethical sensitivity toward social, environmental, cultural, and economic issues within their communities.

Rasheed et al. (2022) examined CSR activities conducted by Pentecostal churches in Ikeja, Lagos State, during the COVID-19 lockdown, as there was initially little focus on the social and health impacts of the pandemic on church members. A cross-sectional descriptive survey was used, with data collected through questionnaires administered face-to-face. The results showed that Pentecostal churches actively engaged in CSR during the lockdown, with their efforts being well-received by congregants. The churches provided support to the less privileged and needy, leading to a positive perception of their CSR initiatives. In an earlier study, Adewale (2020) investigated the role of Pentecostal churches, specifically the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), in CSR. Adewale aimed to explore RCCG’s socio-economic

activities, community development programmes, and women empowerment initiatives. Using both primary and secondary sources and analytical methods, the research employs Weber's theory on the spirit of capitalism and Durkheim's functionalism to examine the church's capitalist tendencies and their impact on community development. Adewale (2020) revealed that RCCG is actively engaged in CSR, contributing to community healthcare, education, infrastructure development, and housing.

Rodríguez-Domínguez and Gallego-Alvarez (2021) investigated the influence of various religions on the adoption of CSR practices by organisations. Utilising Stakeholder and Legitimacy theories, the study examined whether religious beliefs contribute to a broader range of CSR initiatives. Analysing a dataset of 13,884 firm-year observations from 30 countries, the findings indicated that religions like Christianity, Judaism, and Buddhism positively impact the adoption of CSR practices, leading companies in regions with higher adherence to these religions to engage more in CSR activities. Conversely, Islam, Hinduism, and Folk religions show a negative correlation. Similarly, in Nigeria, Adamu et al. (2024) examined the role of faith-based organisations in implementing CSR initiatives aimed at supporting orphanages. With high poverty levels and a significant number of orphaned children in need, Adamu et al. (2024) noted that these organisations undertake various charitable activities as part of their religious obligations. The research, conducted through a literature review and case study analysis, highlighted CSR initiatives such as providing basic needs, healthcare services, and educational support. The findings emphasised the positive impact of these initiatives on orphanages and the communities they serve.

From a Christian theological perspective, Setiawan et al. (2021) explored CSR initiatives to encourage Christian businesspeople to recognise the importance of CSR beyond economic success, particularly in response to legitimacy pressures from stakeholders. The research is a qualitative, multidisciplinary, phenomenological study that uses literature review techniques to align CSR practices with the 10 principles of the United Nations Global Compact (UNGC) and Christian faith. The study identified the lack of multidisciplinary research on CSR and the results of the research served as a companion in generating new business ideas that are in line with Christian faith in various seminars, workshops and group discussions. Paula (2018) examined the Catholic teachings on social responsibility. The approach used in the study was descriptive. The study discovered that social responsibility entails a moral imperative to behave in the community's best interests. Adeyemi (2014) explored the approach of the Redeemed Christian Church of God North America (RCCGNA) CSR with a focus on the Church's apparent lack of engagement with CSR and advocating its adoption as a Church tradition. The study also aimed to demonstrate how CSR could serve as a tool for community integration and development. Utilising both quantitative and qualitative research methods, the findings revealed that embracing CSR would directly and indirectly benefit the RCCGNA by making the Church more community-oriented, fostering greater acceptance, spiritual receptivity, and positive responses from both the Church and the broader American public. The study concluded that implementing CSR practices could lead to the establishment of a Church-wide policy that embeds the core principles of CSR across all RCCGNA locations.

Dominik and Florian (2020) explored the relationship between religion and CSR with the aim of providing the first comprehensive evaluation of research in this area. The study utilised secondary data through a review of existing literature. The findings suggested that religiously inspired moral attitudes may often be superficial and that it remains uncertain whether these religiously motivated views are consistently upheld in everyday business practices. Another noteworthy study by MacDonald (2019) investigated the interaction between the Church and CSR, employing a social methodology within an ecclesiological framework. The study's findings addressed questions about the future of the community and the role of religion in society, concluding that human dignity and value are consistently upheld in a responsible society despite opposing forces. MacDonald (2019) recommended that the Church should continue to address these challenges while remaining committed to promoting justice in the present world. In their study, Sessa, Malandrino, and Sica (2020) examined the influence of the Church's Social Doctrine (SDC) on the rapid expansion of the CSR concept. Through critical analysis, the study concluded that the SDC serves as a suitable framework for implementing the principles of CSR. This, in turn, supports the adoption of socially sustainable management strategies. The findings were based on an analysis of various encyclicals, particularly the "Economy of Communion" approach proposed by Chiara Lubich. Furthermore, Helmi (2020) conducted an exploratory study on Islamic microfinance institutions, specifically examining how Islamic Corporate Social Responsibility (i-CSR) principles were implemented at BMT UGT Sidogiri, an Islamic microfinance company affiliated with an Islamic boarding school in Indonesia. The study utilised a qualitative approach and found that CSR was effectively implemented within this Islamic microfinance institution, largely due to its alignment (convergence) with traditional CSR models. The study concluded that implementing Islamic ethical obligations involves conducting transactions in accordance with Islamic ethics and embodying the traits of the Prophet as an ideal leader.

A recurring theme in the reviewed literature is the significance of CSR in enhancing the image and reputation of religious faith within society. However, none of the existing studies have specifically addressed how this can be effectively implemented within a faith-based NGO. This study fills this gap by investigating how ADRA Nigeria, a faith-based NGO, is advancing the agenda of the social gospel through its CSR initiatives.

Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on two related theories—the social support and the Great Commission theories. The social support theory was initially conceived as a theory for addressing social delinquency. The proponents of social support theory such as Cullen, Wright and Chamlin (1999), are of the view that when individuals have some level of support to take care of their needs, they are most likely not to engage in social vices. Such support could come from individual or collective effort such as the government or even non-governmental organisations (Cullen et al., 1999). Kurt-Butler (2018) sees social support theory as an agent of social and cultural reforms. In this study, social support is considered an essential antidote and an essential mitigating factor to social deprivation, depression, and sudden death (Kurt-Butler, 2018). People in difficult situations occasioned by social upheaval, war, natural disasters, and such

other unforeseen and extreme circumstances can easily give up on life. In some other situations, they may resort to crime and other anti-social behaviours for survival. Research suggests that communities that are able to provide higher levels of social support have lower rates of juvenile crime. Social support is also considered as an important element of adolescent well-being. To this end, therefore, social support can be a key factor in rehabilitating both juvenile offenders and for positively re-orienting even adults that are at the threshold of crime as a last resort for survival. This is where the social welfare programmes of the Church find appeal. Such programmes have the capacity of reducing social ill and bringing about sanity within the society. By providing aid and succour to those in need, the Church shows a deliberate concern for empathy and social stability.

The Great Commission theory is derived from the command of Jesus Christ in Matthew 28:18-20 to His disciples to go into the whole world and make disciples for Him. According to Okere (2019), this command implies that Christian Communicators should find empowerment to live a life of service to God and humanity by preparing the world for peaceful living here on planet earth and in anticipation of the world to come in eternity. It therefore means that communicating the gospel and making disciples for Jesus Christ is not limited to preaching the Word but living the Word through acts of kindness, charity and love. There can be no greater way of doing this than by meeting the needs of the less privileged in the society. This dimension of the Great Commission theory finds direct application in both the parable of the Good Samaritan in Luke 10:30-37 and the parable of the sheep and the goats in Matthew 25:31-46. In both parables, Jesus emphasised the fact that acts of love, kindness and empathy are very effective means of making disciples for Him. It is in this wise that we find the Great Commission theory relevant to this study.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. Data were collected with the use of in-depth key informant interviews conducted with the Director of ADRA-Nigeria and five beneficiaries of the organisation's services in three Nigeria's Northeastern states of Adamawa, Borno, and Yobe, which were ravaged by the Boko Haram terrorist group. Decision on the choice of the locations of the study and respondents was arrived at through purposive sampling technique, which is a type of non-probability sampling technique, whereby researchers choose individuals of the public to participate in their surveys based on certain criteria set by the researcher (Nyimbili & Nyimbili, 2024). The criteria used for selecting the participants were as follows: Being a major decision-maker and influencer of the operations of the institution (as in the case of the ADRA Director), being a beneficiary of the CSR efforts of ADRA-Nigeria; living/residing in the Boko Haram enclave; and being non-members of the Seventh-day Adventist Church; and expression of willingness to participate in the interview process. The data generated through the interviews were analysed qualitatively.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This discussion is a synthesis of the in-depth interviews with Mr. Fred Omosebi, the Country Director of ADRA-Nigeria and the five selected recipients of the CSR efforts of ADRA-Nigeria in Nigeria's Northeastern states of Adamawa, Borno, and Yobe, with the aim and objectives expressed in the introduction of this paper.

In response to the first research question which establishes the ways through which ADRA, Nigeria presents the social gospel through her corporate social responsibility effort, Mr. Fred Omosebi, the Country Director of ADRA-Nigeria shed light on the issue thus:

ADRA, Nigeria was originally founded to meet the needs of the less fortunate in the society. As a philanthropic arm of the Seventh-day Adventist Church, ADRA-Nigeria's, primary goal is to provide humanitarian assistance to the most disadvantaged members of the society. Since its inception, ADRA has been actively involved in a wide range of humanitarian endeavours throughout Nigeria. Many of the projects ADRA-Nigeria has been involved in have focused on women's empowerment across the country, agricultural research and development, and infrastructure construction among others.

He outlined eight major areas on which ADRA Nigeria had made the focal point of her CSR programmes. These are development of underdeveloped communities; embarking on humanitarian projects; women empowerment; health programmes; education programmes; human empowerment, agricultural activities; and relief of the attendant problems of insurgency attacks. ADRA Nigeria's initiatives align closely with the social support theory, which emphasises that social assistance can significantly impact individual and community well-being. This theory posits that providing support—whether through individuals, communities, or organisations—can alleviate social issues and enhance life quality (Cullen, Wright & Chamlin, 1999; Kurt-Butler, 2018). ADRA Nigeria's efforts in areas such as community development, women empowerment, health programmes, and education are clear manifestations of this theory. Elaborating on these areas, Mr Omosebi has this to say:

One of ADRA's key CSR operations is the development of underprivileged communities. ADRA is concentrating more effort in the country's northern part because of its low degree of development. ADRA Nigeria has begun a number of humanitarian projects. The goal of these initiatives is to raise the level of living for the households that live in the communities. Empowerment of women is incorporated in our CSR activities which aim at financially supporting women in local communities, as well as offering different assistance to them so as to increase their income. ADRA Nigeria participates in a variety of health initiatives for the general populace. Since its inception, ADRA Nigeria has launched a number of health initiatives aimed at educating and assisting individuals with various health concerns. Participation in education programmes is one of ADRA Nigeria's CSR efforts. These initiatives are dedicated to assisting underprivileged children and orphans in obtaining an education. Aside from assisting children, ADRA Nigeria also participates in higher education programmes. ADRA Nigeria empowers Nigerians by assisting them in launching their

businesses by providing the necessary funds or an important asset. ADRA Nigeria also engages in agricultural operations with rural farmers. This is accomplished by providing various feeds, nutrients, and fertilizers to farmers in rural communities to help them with their varied farming operations.

Mr Omosebi, also explained that they were deliberate in reaching out to victims of insurgency attacks. ADRA Nigeria was ready to help these people in their hours of need. The Director emphasised that ADRA Nigeria has a large number of agents in the country's north to aid victims of Boko-haram assaults. One of the many advantages of ADRA's CSR activities is that they are not restricted to any one group, but are instead made open to the broader public regardless of religion, gender, race, or tribe.

The Great Commission theory, derived from Jesus Christ's command to spread the gospel through acts of service (Matthew 28:18-20), also frames ADRA Nigeria's CSR efforts. This theory emphasises that fulfilling the gospel involves not just preaching but living out Christian values through acts of kindness and service. ADRA Nigeria's mission to provide humanitarian aid to all individuals, regardless of their religion or background, embodies this principle of universal compassion. According to Mr Omosebi, ADRA was founded to support and assist human growth, with no ulterior motive either for profit or any other hidden objective; it is all about meeting the mission of God's word. Despite being a Christian organisation, ADRA Nigeria does not confine its services to Christians only. Mr Omosebi emphasised that the purpose of ADRA Nigeria's CSR initiatives is to fulfill God's commandment. According to him, Jesus spoke about the benefits of assisting the poor, which is the primary goal of ADRA Nigeria. The Director emphasised that 'the delight and motivation for the activities is to achieve the divine aim of having a beneficial influence on earth while also eventually making heaven'. According to the recipients, ADRA improved their families' livelihoods by providing monetary assistance, capital assets (Grinding machine, Pop-corn machine, and Spaghetti machine), fertilizer, crops, and other supplementary products. This was corroborated by the recipients, who stated that ADRA Nigeria has aided in the growth of numerous houses in the neighbourhood in which they live. The organisation's focus on developing underprivileged communities in northern Nigeria addresses significant social disparities and fosters stability, mirroring the social support theory's claim that such support can prevent negative social outcomes and promote well-being.

The literature review shows how faith-based NGOs like ADRA Nigeria engage in CSR motivated by religious values rather than material gain. This is supported by studies examining the intersection of faith and CSR, which emphasise that such organisations contribute significantly to community development through charitable activities (Jintao et al., 2020; Al-Ma'ani et al., 2019). ADRA Nigeria's CSR initiatives, such as community development, health programmes, and educational support, align with these findings by demonstrating how faith-based organisations can effectively integrate CSR into their mission. Furthermore, the review identifies a gap in literature regarding the specific implementation of CSR within faith-based NGOs. ADRA's detailed approach to addressing various societal needs provides a practical example of how these organisations can merge religious motivations with CSR practices. This

therefore contributes to the broader discourse on faith-based CSR practices (Rodríguez-Domínguez & Gallego-Alvarez, 2021; Adamu et al., 2024).

The second research question aimed to explore the perceptions of recipients regarding ADRA Nigeria's CSR efforts, specifically in the context of the social gospel. The data, gathered through interviews with five beneficiaries of ADRA's initiatives, provides insightful reflections on how these programs are perceived and their impact on the recipients' lives. The recipients' feedback aligns closely with the social support theory and the Great Commission theory discussed earlier. The social support theory suggests that providing targeted assistance can significantly enhance individuals' economic and social well-being (Cullen et al., 1999). The positive responses from the recipients reflect this theory's premise. For example, Mrs. Adeola from Yola expressed her delight in how ADRA's CSR initiatives have notably improved her economic situation and the broader community. This sentiment is supported by other recipients, such as Hannatu from Yobe State, who highlighted the benefits of ADRA's women empowerment programmes. These testimonials reflect the effectiveness of ADRA's initiatives in providing essential support, thereby reinforcing the social support theory's claim that such efforts contribute significantly to alleviating social and economic challenges.

Moreover, the favourable perception of ADRA Nigeria's CSR efforts among the recipients underlines the application of the Great Commission theory. This theory emphasises the importance of living out Christian values through acts of service and kindness (Matthew 28:18-20). The positive feedback from recipients, such as Yusuf from Borno State, who praised ADRA's kindness and expressed that 'those ADRA people are good people. They truly show that they worship God. They are very kind. They helped me and my family'. Yusuf's statement reflects how ADRA's actions resonate with the principles of the Great Commission. By providing aid and support to individuals regardless of their background, ADRA Nigeria embodies the Christian mandate to serve humanity and fulfill divine commandments. The recipients' appreciation of ADRA's work as an expression of genuine faith and kindness supports the Great Commission theory's emphasis on integrating religious principles with practical humanitarian efforts.

The literature review on faith-based NGOs and their CSR practices further contextualises these findings. Jintao et al. (2020), for instance, stresses that organisations motivated by religious values often achieve a positive impact on their beneficiaries. ADRA Nigeria's CSR initiatives, which include economic empowerment, health support, and relief efforts, align with this understanding. The recipients' positive perceptions of ADRA's impact corroborate the Adamu et al.'s (2024) assertion that faith-driven CSR can effectively address social needs and foster positive relationships between organisations and communities. Hence, ADRA Nigeria's CSR activities are perceived by the recipients not only as effective in improving their economic conditions but also as genuine expressions of Christian service.

The third and final research question investigates the challenges faced by ADRA Nigeria in presenting the social gospel through its corporate social responsibility (CSR) efforts. According to Mr. Fred Omosebi, the Director of ADRA Nigeria, several key obstacles hinder the organisation's ability to effectively deliver on its humanitarian mission. Mr Omosebi said one

of their major challenges is the state of the economy. He said that ‘the Nigerian economy is not promising, and this has an impact on many of the financing activities that ADRA gets from donors’. This situation aligns with the study of Emmanuel and Gernah (2022) on the impact of economic conditions on non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and their ability to implement social programmes. Economic instability can constrain resources available for CSR activities, limiting the scope and effectiveness of humanitarian efforts.

In addition to economic factors, security concerns are a major impediment. According to Mr. Omosebi, ‘staff and team members are discouraged from joining or even traveling to specific villages, particularly those in the north, due to concerns about security’. This insecurity impacts ADRA Nigeria’s ability to reach and assist communities in need, reflecting a broader issue faced by NGOs operating in conflict zones (Uzuegbunam, 2013). The safety of personnel is crucial for the successful implementation of CSR initiatives, and ongoing security threats can severely restrict operational capacity.

Language barriers further complicate ADRA Nigeria’s CSR efforts. With approximately 300 languages spoken across Nigeria, including over 50 in Taraba State alone, communication challenges are significant. Mr. Omosebi emphasised that many staff members struggle to understand local languages due to the limited proficiency in English among rural populations. He noted that ‘the issue arises in ADRA Nigeria’s staff/team comprehending the languages of the areas they visit. Because of the weak education system in these rural areas, relatively few of them learn English to help with interpretation’. The lack of effective communication can impede the successful execution of projects and limit the organisation’s ability to connect with local communities. Closely linked to language barrier is the challenge of multiplicity of cultures. Nigeria’s rich cultural landscape includes variations in customs and practices that can impact the acceptance and implementation of CSR activities. Mr Omosebi lamented the fact that ‘some cultures in Nigeria are not hospitable, making it difficult to stay or even perform CSR in such communities’. Understanding and navigating these cultural complexities are crucial for ensuring the success of CSR initiatives.

CONCLUSION

This study evaluated the CSR efforts of ADRA-Nigeria and their impact on the welfare of communities in Northeastern Nigeria. The findings reveal that ADRA has largely fulfilled its mission from its inception to the present, particularly in regions affected by Boko Haram insurgencies, including Adamawa, Borno, and Yobe states. The organisation’s commitment to social gospel activities, which double as CSR initiatives, has significantly improved living conditions and contributed to human development in these areas. Through its humanitarian work, ADRA has proven to be a reliable and successful agent in enhancing the quality of life and supporting the social and economic upliftment of affected communities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. To maintain its social and spiritual relevance, alongside the continued assurance of the temporal and spiritual wellbeing of Nigerian citizens in general, ADRA-Nigeria should sustain its corporate social responsibility efforts. This is especially because of its observed, combined usefulness in alleviating human sufferings and preparing souls for the Kingdom of God, which is supposed to be the ultimate aim of any faith-based NGO.
2. Based on the observed success of ADRA-Nigeria in becoming a reliable faith-based NGO for alleviating human suffering, through social gospel practices hinged on the principles of humanitarianism and CSR, it is herein recommended that other Christian denominations should emulate its template of investment in various social gospel/CSR activities through their NGOs for the same purpose. This will be of great benefit to the beneficiaries as well as in enhancing the corporate image of the Church among non-Christians.
3. In contemporary times, the presence of ADRA-Nigeria is majorly felt in Northern Nigeria. Therefore, there is the need for ADRA-Nigeria to extend its services to some other parts of the country for alleviating the same or similar humanitarian challenges.
4. The Government should intensify its efforts at the attempts to stem-the tide of insecurity across the country and especially in the harshly terrorised Northeastern states, which were the focus of this study. This is because, ADRA-Nigeria and other faith-based NGOs in Nigeria can never reach the apogee of their expected achievements in reaching out to most of the affected citizens unless the teeming insecurity in the country is reduced to the barest minimum or even totally resolved.

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